

No Robot is an Island: An Always-On Cognitive Architecture for Social Context Awareness in Dynamic Environments*

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Abstract— Robots must continuously perceive, learn, and adapt to function autonomously in dynamic environments. Aligning with the Artificial Cognition (ACo) approach, we present an Always-On cognitive architecture enabling robots to continuously perceive and build a self-supervised, emergent representation of the environment to support proactive behavior later. The architecture leverages sensor fusion, efficient multimodal in-memory representation of perception, and self-organization of personal experiences through memory consolidation. We validated the system in our laboratory and at the Humanoids 2024 conference. In both venues, the architecture autonomously learned the simple yet foundational distinction between lively intervals of high social activity and calm moments of minimal interaction. Such knowledge will be crucial in kickstarting proactive context-specific behavior. This work contributes to developing truly self-improving robotic agents, paving the way for more intelligent and continuously learning autonomous systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous robots introduced in dynamic social contexts need to promptly learn and adapt to the environment, the people therein, and the emerging social dynamics. The recent research trends in robotics and computer science strongly rely on Deep Learning and Large Language models as the ultimate tool enabling robots to learn and adapt in open-ended environments. Crucial factors of such an approach are (i) collecting a plethora of data, vast enough to contain any possible situation of interest; and (ii) have access to powerful computation capabilities. Then the model can be deployed on a robot, hoping that the encountered situation would fall in the dataset distribution. However, if humans’ capabilities are the reference robots are aiming at, we simply don’t work that way. Humans’ capabilities are acquired through the continual, incremental interaction with the environment and agents therein. The acquired knowledge is highly personal, dependent on the specific embodiment – with its strengths and limitations – and the set of experiences we have been through. Such approach has been recently defined as *Artificial Cognition* (ACo) [1], with a strong reliance on Vernon’s definition of cognition: “the process by which an autonomous system perceives its environment, learns from experience, anticipates the outcome of events, acts to pursue goals, and adapts to changing circumstances” [2]. The goal of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is leveraging encyclopaedical knowledge, bounded by the available data, to execute tasks as humans. In contrast, the goal of Artificial Cognition is to enable the agent to develop the necessary *ontogenetical knowledge* to survive – in a Darwinian sense – and preserve internal consistency [2]. Still an ACo agent starts with a small set of *phylogenetic abilities* to kickstart personal knowledge acquisition, i.e., a cognitive architecture. Cognitive Architectures proved to be highly suitable to endow robots with learning, adaptation, and

decision-making capabilities. Over the past decades, numerous cognitive architectures have been proposed [3]. Classical architectures such as SOAR [4] and ACT-R [5] focus on symbolic reasoning and structured knowledge representation. While these models have proven useful in controlled environments, they struggle to generalize in open-ended, dynamic settings where interactions are unpredictable and context dependent. Embodied and enactive approaches, such as the Subsumption Architecture [6] and Predictive Processing models [7], have attempted to bridge the gap between perception, action, and learning. These approaches emphasize the importance of real-world interaction in shaping cognition. Notably, developmental robotics has emerged as a key research field, exploring how robots can acquire complex behaviors through lifelong learning, akin to human infants [8]. Among the most prominent cognitive architectures for humanoid robots, the Distributed Adaptive Control (DAC) model [9] has been instrumental in integrating perception, action, and motivation-based decision-making. Similarly, the OpenCog framework [10] leverages symbolic and sub-symbolic representations to support autonomous learning. However, these architectures often require extensive pre-programmed structures, limiting their flexibility in emergent, unsupervised learning scenarios.

A. Toward an Emergent Enactive Cognitive Architecture

Given the limitations of existing architectures, we propose an alternative approach rooted in minimalism and emergence [11]. Rather than imposing predefined cognitive models, our enactive cognitive architecture aims to let *cognition* emerge naturally through continuous interaction with the environment. Toward continuous interaction, our architecture is designed to be *always-on*, supporting the agent’s autonomous acquisition and self-organization of personal experiences. Inspired by enactive cognition [2], [11], our approach emphasizes the following principles: **Incremental Learning** – The robot acquires skills progressively, akin to human infants, without predefined tasks. **Embodied Adaptation** – Perception and action are tightly coupled, ensuring adaptive responses to dynamic environments. **Personalized Experience** – Learning is driven by direct, context-specific interactions rather than generic datasets. **Self-Sustaining Cognitive Growth** – Instead of optimizing for pre-set performance metrics, the system prioritizes maintaining internal coherence and autonomy. This bottom-up methodology is currently being implemented in the iCub humanoid robot within the framework of the iCog Initiative¹. By integrating multimodal sensory inputs and real-world social interactions, we aim to create a system capable of developing its own understanding of the world—just as a newborn would. Our goal is not merely to train a robot but to cultivate an evolving artificial cognitive entity, one that grows, learns, and coexists within our shared space, day by day.

¹ <https://icog.eu/>

Figure 1. (left) The Always-On Cognitive architecture for the humanoid robot iCub; (right) Associative Memory Dashboard for demonstration purposes

II. COGNITIVE ARCHITECTURE

As per Vernon’s definition, the first fundamental components of cognition is enabling the embodied system to perceive and learn from the environment it is placed in [2]. Through continually active observation, infants can deduce novelty and regularities, supporting the formation of associative memory and anticipation of events. Similarly, we designed our architecture as a system that (i) actively perceives the environment; and (ii) autonomously organizes and learns patterns from the collected experiences. This preliminary version of the architecture has no explicit “goal”; rather its objective is to detect and model the recurrent patterns of the environment, distinguishing what is known from what is novel, toward “*anticipating the outcome of events*”.

A. Robot and Setup

We embodied the architecture into the ICubHead robot, an actuated head of the humanoid robot iCub, mounted on a stationary 3D-printed upper body (Figure 3). The ICubHead can look around, moving the neck and eyes with 6 DoF. Visual perception happened through two eye-mounted RGB cameras (640x480, 20 fps), while we opted for an external miniDSP ambiMIK-1 microphone for the auditory perception. Due to the limited computational power of the ICubHead robot, only the on-edge perceptual and control modules run on it; the core of the architecture was executed on a DELL PC - Intel Core i7 2.60GHz x 12 - RAM 16 GB – with the two communicating locally via the YARP middleware.

The cognitive architecture comprises four components (Figure 1).

B. Multimodal Perception

The Multimodal Perception module extracts relevant information of the environment from the robot raw perception (Figure 1, blue). It processes raw frames (RGB, 640x480) and audio chunks (44.1 kHz) at 20 Hz, extracting five core features inspired by humans’ early-age development. From the images it computes the *number of faces*, the *number of people gazing toward the robot* (mutual gaze), the *quantity of motion*, and the *illumination*; from the audio, it computes the *right and left root mean square* (RMS). We considered such features the minimal necessary toolset to bootstrap the architecture abilities. Indeed, since the newborn stage, humans display a preference for

attending, and later tracking, human *faces* [12], *sound* [13] and *moving* objects with a preference for biological motion [14]. Around 3 months, infants start engaging in *mutual gaze* with other agents [15], slowly developing the awareness of being the target of others’ attentions, a crucial factor in the development of our personal *self* [16]. Lastly, the *illumination* detection is meant to allow the architecture to recognize different moments of the day. Currently, the system is designed to be used in environments where humans are the main source of movement and auditory noise. Hence, we did not distinguish biological motion and human speech, opting for a lighter processing of the perception. Lastly, the raw audio and video are locally stored for future analysis.

C. Embodied Behavior

To lead the robot attention toward meaningful portions of the environment, we implemented a simple *social motive*, inspired by infants’ tendency on seeking other interactive agents [17]. The Embodied Behavior module (Figure 1, purple) controls the ICubHead: whenever a human face is present in the scene the robot tracks it; otherwise, it alternates between resting or gaze-wandering phases attending random gaze-points looking for faces to track. The observation of different portions of the environment is meant to enable the robot to collect more generalized observations. Also, the module publishes over YARP the joints state of the robot, allowing it to consider its body position in space.

D. Episodes Segmentation

The Episode Segmentation module (Figure 1, red) oversees the real-time partitioning of the robot’s perception into meaningful chunks of experience. This is achieved by constructing two types of objects: *events* and *episodes*. **Events** are time-stamped snapshots of the systems’ internal and external state. At each timestamp, the architecture composes an *event* object by synchronizing the frame and audio chunk with the relative core features and robot joints states. Then, **Episodes** are defined as sequence of *events* belonging to the same experience. We designed the segmentation of events into episodes by taking inspiration from infants’ exploratory motive, i.e., *the continual research of novelties and regularities in the environment* [2]. For each new event, architecture uses the equation below to decide whether it belongs to the current episode’s distribution, or if it is an outlier, suggesting something novel is about to happen in the

environment. The system tracks the mean and standard deviations of the *number of faces* (F), *quantity of motion* (M) and *right/left RMS* (R and L) within the current episode. Each new event is then compared to the episode’s averages, seeking outliers – i.e., observations deviating more than 3 standard deviations from the episode’s mean – separately for each feature. Each one contributes with a different weight to a cumulative sum: $W_F: 0.5$, $W_M: 0.25$, $W_{AR}: 0.125$, $W_{AL}: 0.125$.

$$\sum_{features} W * (|Mean[f] - feature| > 3 * STD[f]) \geq 0.5$$

If the sum of each contribution is equal or greater than 0.5, the current episode is encoded in memory and a new one starts with the outlier event.

E. Associative Memory

The Associative Memory module (Figure 1, yellow) oversees the encoding and efficient organization of the collected episodes. Referring to infants’ memory development stages [18], the first forms of memory allow children to develop simple associations between repeated episodes – usually mediated by feeling and comfort – supporting expectation and prediction. Such associations do not require active explicit recall of a specific episode but rather appear as an unconscious gut feeling. Similarly, we designed an *implicit associative memory* offering a primitive form of **Recognition**, i.e., understanding if the just-experienced episode is known and to which group of associated episodes it belongs to; and **Temporal Expectation**, i.e., based on past episodes in the same context and timeframe, determine whether the episode is consistent or not.

1) Encoding

Whenever an episode ends, the architecture stores in an SQLite database the synchronized core feature, the joints state and the timestamp of each event. Similarly, it stores the mean and standard deviation of the core features within the episode along with its temporal begin and end. Lastly, it aggregates the episode’s frames and audio chunks in .wav and .mp4 files respectively. Such raw data is then encoded as embeddings using two pretrained models. For the video, we opted for the *SlowFast* [19] model as it is designed for action understanding in realistic environments, aligning with infants increased interests on humans’ movements. For the audio, we relied on the *VGGish* [20] since it is trained to extract features from generic waveforms. Specifically, the 128-long video embedding produced by the SlowFast model is concatenated to the average of the two 128-long embeddings of the right and left audio channels generated by VGGish, resulting in a 512-long multimodal embedding. Episodes’ embeddings are stored in the SQLite database too.

2) Consolidation

At the end of each day, the architecture self-organizes all the episodes collected so far, learning new associations. At this purpose, it trains two self-supervised models: an UMAP [21] model to represent the 512-long embeddings in 2 dimensions; and an HDBSCAN [22] model, to cluster the reduced datapoints, highlighting similar episodes. We opted for UMAP thanks to its efficient scaling on datasets of increasing dimensions, while HDBSCAN has been proved to be robust

against distribution of non-deterministic shape and varying density. To improve the memory representation, the system applies grid-search optimization, looking for the UMAP and HDBSCAN parameters that maximize the clusters’ *silhouette score*. As a result, each episode is labeled with an associated cluster.

3) Recognition

The UMAP and HDBSCAN models are then used in real-time. After storing an episode, its 512-long embedding representation is reduced with UMAP model and labelled with HDBSCAN.

4) Temporal Expectation

Lastly, after at least one day of operation, the architecture can leverage the past episodes, to guess the most probable cluster of episodes that should take place at a given time. Whenever an episode is recognized – i.e., it is not considered an outlier – its label is compared with the expected one in the same time windows, identifying recurrent temporal patterns or novel experiences.

III. VALIDATION

In the next development iteration we will focus on closing the loop, leveraging episodes recognition and expectation-based novelty detection to enable the ICubHead proactive behavior in the environment.

However, before going any further, we deemed it necessary to verify that (i) our Episodes Segmentation approach can generate significant chunks of the robot’s perception; (ii) that such episodes can be represented in memory via embeddings; and (iii) that the embeddings can be organized in a meaningful representation of the robot’s experiences.

The validation took place in two stages: firstly, we tested the architecture in our office for 5 consecutive days; then, we explored its generalizability by bringing the system as a demonstration at three major robotics and computer science conferences: ICRA@40 (Rotterdam), ECCV 2024 (Milan), and Humanoids 2024 (Nancy). This manuscript focuses on the in-lab and Humanoids 2024 validation.

A. In-Lab Validation

We placed the ICubHead robot in our open office (Figure 2). The area hosts four researchers’ desks, while up to 10 people could pass by during the day. The room becomes empty at lunchtime and during events involving the group. The ICubHead was positioned close to our break area, where we keep treats to be shared among the group. This zone is highly crowded after lunch, while it is sporadically visited during the day. The robot was oriented so that while gaze-wondering it could look at any portion of the room, including the windows on its left. We kept the ICubHead active for 5 consecutive days – i.e., a work week – from 10 AM to 4 PM. We excluded the first day as it has been used to tune the setup such as microphone volume and robot placement. Hence, the resulting dataset comprises 24 hours of recording. During the data collection, our colleagues were asked to keep their usual habits to ensure the naturalness of the collected data.

Figure 2. Incremental representation of the episodes in the architecture’s associative memory during the four days of *in-Lab* data collection. (Up) Optimal UMAP representation of the embeddings, clustered with HDBSCAN; (Down) Temporal displacement divided by cluster. Outliers in gray.

1) Results

The architecture collected 449 ($M=112$, $SD=83$) episodes, distributed resembling the open space occupation of those days: two researchers were present on *day1* (19 eps.); four on *day2* (217 eps.), and *day3* (130 eps.); lastly, on *day4* (83 eps.), a single person was in the room with others coming sporadically.

Figure 3. The ICubHead robot observing our office during a coffee break

On average, 90% of the episodes were collected between 1 and 2 PM, i.e., during our usual after-lunch break. Episodes in such a timeframe were also the shortest: on average, 1-minute long w.r.t. 25 minutes in the remaining time. We speculate that the higher population in the room would generate a higher variability in the multimodal perception, causing more outliers and, hence, more scattered episodes. Figure 2 represents the evolution of the associative memory along the four days of activity. At the end of each day, the system tried to find the optimal UMAP representation and HDBSCAN clustering of the episodes collected so far. Since *day1* the architecture managed to find a meaningful representation (*silhouette* = 0.65); then refined during *day2* (*silhouette* = 0.74), and *day3* (*silhouette* = 0.58). At the end of the week, the associative memory of the ICubHead found an optimal 2D representation with two clusters and a silhouette score of 0.69. To better unfold and evaluate such representation, we grounded it with respect to the episodes-averaged core features of the perception. We fitted a mixed model for each of the mean core features: we considered the outlier-filtered ‘cluster’ label as a fixed factor and added the ‘day’ of recording as random effect.

Cluster 0 (Figure 2, Up, Day4, orange) showed a higher number of faces ($B=1.668$, $t=14.88$, $p<0.001$), mutual gazes ($B=0.045$, $t=2.44$, $p<0.001$), quantity of motion ($B=0.421$, $t=6.31$, $p<0.001$), and audio RMS ($B=6.56$, $t=5.59$, $p<0.001$) with respect to the other cluster. Such episodes could be related to **LIVELY** moments where multiple people socially interact in the room. Indeed, observing the temporal distribution of the clusters (Figure 2, Down, Day4), 91% of the **LIVELY** episodes occurred between 1-1:30 PM, overlapping with our usual coffee break interval. On the other hand, episodes in cluster 1 (Figure 2, Up, Day4, blue) were longer ($B=-459$, $t=-6.52$, $p<0.001$) and presented a higher illumination ($B=-0.099$, $t=-10.6$, $p<0.001$). We speculate it groups **CALM** episodes where either there was nobody in the room or the few ones were working at their desks, causing less perceptual novelties. Indeed, 90% of them took place during working hours (see Figure 3, right). Also, we deem particularly interesting the higher illumination of **CALM** episodes: while gaze-wandering without faces to track, the ICubHead would look more often at the high-illumination area of the window on its left (see Figure 3). This supports the great importance of the agent’s embodiment, its capabilities, and its displacement in the environment in relation to the formation of personal and located memories.

Summing up, in just a few days the architecture managed to autonomously refine the simple yet fundamental distinction between **LIVELY** and **CALM** episodes. Notably, the learnt distinction is specific to our environment – i.e., a work office with predefined working hours and rest times – with its own rules and regularities. Different environments – or even different placement within them – are supposed to elicit the formation of different memory structures. Good cognitive architectures should be able to unfold the underlying structure and specific rules of the environment without depending on a specific one to work properly. That’s it, a good system should be able to generalize. Hence, the second validation stage.

B. Humanoids 2024 Validation

The International Conference on Humanoid Robots (Humanoids) took place in Nancy (France) from the 22nd to the 24th of November 2024. We brought the ICubHead and architecture as an exhibition within IIT stands (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Incremental representation of the episodes in the architecture’s associative memory during the four days of **Humanoids 2024** data collection. (Up) Optimal UMAP representation of the embeddings, clustered with HDBSCAN; (Down) Temporal displacement divided by cluster. Outliers in gray.

The architecture remained functionally the same; we just added two features for demonstration purposes. Firstly, we enabled the system to **consolidate the memory at any time**, by bringing the agent into a resting state of suppressed perception similar to a powernap [23]. This on-demand consolidation allows the system to update its own representation of the world and ability to recognize episodes. Notably, the trigger of memory consolidation is still manual, but we plan to integrate the mechanism in the architecture. Secondly, we added a **dashboard** module (Figure 1, right) (i) to trigger the consolidation, (ii) to visualize in real-time the reduced and clustered memory of the agent, and (iii) to compute and visualize statistical differences grounding the unsupervised clusters with respect to the perceptual features (Figure 1, right). Lastly, the dashboard allows users to hover on an episode datapoint reproducing its stored video and audio, to better unfold the learnt distinction.

Figure 5. The ICubHead robot at the Humanoids 2024 conference.

Accommodating our attendance to the event, the architecture stayed active for a varying amount of time each day: (*day1*) from 10 to 11 AM and from 2 to 5 PM; (*day2*) from 2 to 6 PM; and (*day3*) from 9 AM to 2 PM – 15 total hours. Visitors were informed the system was recording audio and video – also visible on a TV screen. Such raw data was retained only for the duration of the event.

1) Results

The architecture collected 2304 episodes ($M=768$, $SD=270$) – 476 on *day1*, 817 on *day2*, and 1011 on *day3*. On average, episodes last 15 seconds ($SD=9$). The system segmented more episodes with lower duration than in the lab, even if it stayed active for less time. This most likely reflects what happened during the **LIVELY** period in the laboratory: the higher activity of the conference – with people continuously passing by – triggered more often the Episodes Segmentation module, producing more scattered episodes. Figure 4 represents the evolution of the associative memory during the three days of the conference. At the end of each day, the architecture tried to find the optimal UMAP representation and HDBSCAN clustering of the episodes collected so far. A separation between episodes is visible since *day1* (*silhouette*=0.65) and then refined during *day2* (*silhouette*=0.65). At the end of the conference, the associative memory of the ICubHead achieved a silhouette score of 0.67, identifying two clusters (see Figure 4, Up, Day3, $N=638$ outliers in gray). As before, we grounded the unsupervised clusters with respect to the core features used to segment episodes. We fitted a mixed model for each of the episode-averaged core features: we considered the outlier-filtered ‘cluster’ label as a fixed factor and added the ‘day’ of as random effect. Cluster 0 (Figure 4, $N=654$ in orange) showed a higher number of faces ($B=0.967$, $t=35.4$, $p<0.001$), mutual gazes ($B=0.086$, $t=15.82$, $p<0.001$), quantity of motion ($B=2.98$, $t=42.9$, $p<0.001$), audio RMS ($B=1.05$, $t=21.0$, $p<0.001$) and episode duration ($B=2.39$, $t=4.71$, $p<0.001$) with respect to Cluster 1 (Figure 5, $N=1012$ in blue). Cluster 0 episodes are most likely related to **LIVELY** moments in which people visited the demonstration boot and actively interacted with the ICubHead. Cluster 1 instead would group **CALM** episodes where a few visitors attended the demo boot. The episodes temporal displacement supports such hypotheses (see Figure 5, lower, day4): 61% of the **LIVELY** episodes occurred between 2 and 4 PM – overlapping with the afternoon coffee break of the conference; similarly **CALM** episodes were

scattered during the days, with 75% of them aligned with talk sessions – cf. Humanoids 2024 program².

Summing up, our architecture successfully learned a meaningful representation of its experiences, even in the more chaotic and unpredictable environment of a conference. The system consistently distinguished **LIVELY** from **CALM** episodes, proving our approach can well generalize among different contexts.

C. Uniformed Memory Representation

Figure 6. Clustering of the full associative memory comprising episodes from both our laboratory and the Humanoids 2024 conference.

Lastly, we merged the episodes’ embeddings from the lab and humanoids conference and learnt a new uniformed representation. The resulting associative memory (see Figure 6) correctly distinguishes episodes from the venues with an accuracy of 98.7%. This is a sanity check of the multimodal embeddings we obtained by concatenating the video and average audio embeddings. Moreover, within each venue, the distinction between **LIVELY** from **CALM** is preserved³. In the lab (Figure 6, left), cluster 2 presents a higher number of faces ($B=1.98$, $t=18.61$, $p<0.001$), mutual gazes ($B=0.035$, $t=2.32$, $p<0.001$), quantity of motion ($B=0.36$, $t=5.53$, $p<0.001$), and audio RMS ($B=7.39$, $t=7.22$, $p<0.001$) with respect to cluster 0. The latter instead shows higher duration ($B=-472$, $t=-5.95$, $p<0.001$), and illumination ($B=-0.121$, $t=-13.2$, $p<0.001$) with respect to the former – consistently with what reported in section A1. At Humanoids (Figure 6, right), cluster 3 shows a higher number of faces ($B=0.974$, $t=39.4$, $p<0.001$), mutual gaze ($B=0.09$, $t=20.5$, $p<0.001$), quantity of motion ($B=2.78$, $t=39.1$, $p<0.001$), audio RMS ($B=0.95$, $t=19.1$, $p<0.001$), and duration ($B=2.60$, $t=5.15$, $p<0.001$) with respect to cluster 1 – as reported in section B1.

IV. DISCUSSION

We presented the first version of our developmental-inspired cognitive architecture for the humanoid robot ICub. Infants incrementally learn how to behave and act through the continual interaction with the environment and agents therein. Similarly, our architecture is designed to be *Always-On*, enabling robotic agents to continuously perceive and build a self-supervised, emergent representation of the environment, to later support proactive behavior.

During two data collections, we validated architecture’s ability to autonomously segment its perception into *episodes* and to self-organize experiences in memory. Firstly, in our

open space, and then at the Humanoids 2024 conference – to further prove the generalization of our approach. In both venues, the architecture learned to distinguish between **LIVELY** episodes – characterized by higher number of faces, mutual gazes, quantity of motion and audio – from **CALM** episodes (see Figure 3 and 5, upper row). Moreover, **LIVELY** episodes mostly overlapped with coffee breaks in our office and at the conference (see Figure 3 and 5, lower row) – i.e., intervals of higher activity, human presence and social interactions – validating such distinction in absence of supervised ground truth. Such simple, primordial, distinction holds crucial potential in enabling the agent to autonomously and proactively act in the environment. For instance, it could make the agent aware of when it is socially acceptable and meaningful to interact, and – even more importantly – when to *expect* interaction from other agents. Indeed, being able to “read the room”, i.e., recognize the kind of experience the agent is currently living is the first, foundational, step toward an agent that “anticipates the outcome of events, acts to pursue goals, and adapts to changing circumstances” [2]. Lastly, we explored the combination of memories from the two venues. The uniformed associative memory representation accurately distinguished episodes related to the two different contexts. This could be nontrivial due to the fundamental characteristics of embeddings and similarity distance; however, it validates that the embeddings’ characteristics are preserved when building a concatenated multimodal representation. Furthermore, the context-specific distinction between **LIVELY** and **CALM** episodes is preserved; enabling the agent to act consistently with the context and location it is living in.

At the current development stage, the architecture presents a few limitations and room for improvement. The novelty-based *Episodes Segmentation* generates too many scattered episodes, especially in high-activity periods (e.g., during the coffee breaks), due to the rapid changes in the core features computed by the *Multimodal Perception* module. The segmentation module should be able to recognize that, despite the occurrence of a perceptual novelty, such an interesting event could still be part of the current episode. A possible solution could be to aggregate similar consecutive episodes as part of the memory consolidation process. Otherwise, an alternative approach could draw inspiration from humans’ short-term (STM) and long-term memory (LTM) [24]. Consecutive *events* could be aggregated in a STM episode of predefined temporal dimension (e.g., 30 seconds [24]). Once they expired, the STM episode would be compared with the currently active LTM episode: if too-similar the former would be merged with the currently active episode; otherwise, a different-enough would be stored as a standalone memory, replacing the currently active one. Such predefined time window would also enable the architecture to perform a recognition of the episode w.r.t. its associative memory, without waiting for the end of the episode. Furthermore, the *novelty*-based segmentation could be replaced by a *curiosity*-inspired one [25]. When something interesting – e.g. diverging from the core features mean – occurs, rather than segmenting a new episode, it could be better to keep up the attention; for instance, by increasing the STM window. A second limitation is that the *Memory Consolidation* process is solely incremental: new episodes are added to the previously stored ones, and a

² <https://2024.ieee-humanoids.org/program-glance/>

³ Analysis performed with mixed effect models as in sections A1 and B1

new representation is learned. To properly scale, while keeping the system always-on, the architecture needs to implement *forgetting* and *reinforcement* mechanisms, keeping only the memories that really matter. Furthermore, the *Multimodal Perception* module computes a predefined set of features inspired by literature development and learning; however, other context- or goal-, specific features could be relevant for the system. Similarly, no semantic information is currently available to the system, i.e., the agent knows how many faces are in front of it, or that there is movement, but it is not aware of *what* is happening, *which actions* are performed, *who* is performing them, or even which *objects* are visible. Such information would help better separating episodes in memory, enabling the agent to behave consistently.

Lastly, to correctly determine what needs to be included in the architecture memories, it is firstly necessary to define *what matters* for the robotic agent. That's it, a *value system* is needed. A social robot would prioritize meeting people and seek interesting interaction; while a collaborative industrial robot would prioritize task competition, efficiency and safety. Similarly, other internal drives – e.g., *energy*, *curiosity*, *boredom* or *comfortability* [26], [27] – could lead the robot's behavior. Defining what drives the robotic agent would also shape its *goal* in the environment and define the set of possible *actions* that the agent could perform to achieve it. Lastly, closing the loop, the episodes' cluster labeling would be crucial to determine the most suitable action to be performed in each moment, with respect to past experiences, to achieve the agent's goal. This will be our objective in the next development iteration: we plan to leverage the clustered past experiences and real-time episodes recognition to let the robot autonomously learn the most suitable action to be performed.

V. CONCLUSION

Developing robotic agents aiming to replicate humans' capabilities is highly challenging. In this manuscript, we presented our ongoing effort toward developing an emergent enactive Cognitive Architecture for the humanoid robot iCub. This work lays the groundwork for the development of truly autonomous, self-improving robotic systems capable of continuous learning and adaptation, offering exciting prospects for the future of cognitive robotics.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

A special thanks to Carmine Miceli that curated the architecture development during his internship period.

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